

THE ROLE OF COGNITIVE APPROACH ON MYTHOLOGICAL POEMS BY TED HUGHES

Qo'chqorxo'jayeve Muxlisaxon Abdimalik qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19091631>

Abstract

This article shows the mythological poetry of Ted Hughes through the framework of cognitive poetics. Drawing on Peter Stockwell's theoretical model, the study analyzes how readers construct meaning in three of Hughes's myth-based poems: Peleus and Thetis, Arachne, and Ravens. The analysis demonstrates that Hughes reinterprets classical mythology not as a stable narrative tradition but as a dynamic cognitive structure that invites active reader participation.

Key words:

Ted Hughes, cognitive poetics, mythological poetry, Peter Stockwell, conceptual metaphor, schema theory, postmodern mythology, reader interpretation.

Ted Hughes is one of the giants in British poetry. His work was delicately done about nature and myth, how people are sensible in postmodern era towards the nature and poetry. He mixes poetry, myth and nature in one symbolizing the human self. He was born in Yorkshire. That's why his poetic vision comes from green villages, countryside of England, enriching his poetic voices with nature and engagement with natural elements and existence. His poetry is usually about the ancient narratives returning as decorative allusions. However, as living structures through which postmodern psychological and moral realities are explored, he has got huge fascination with myth, which is especially clear and evident in "Tales from Ovid", where he translates, where he reinterprets classical myth with visceral immediacy, and especially in poems such as Arachne and Ravens, where mythic figures come with contemporary psychological experience. It is often described by postmodern theorists that Hughes translated the Ovid's mythological stories into his own postmodern images, in his book "Tales from Ovid". They just don't make classical narratives, but they change the fragmentation and put the psychological depths and ambiguity. Hughes don't just give the stable meanings or didactic conclusions like conventional myth. These poems invite readers to make a active construction, to make their self-conclusion through imagination and emotion. For Hughes, myth becomes a cognitive and experimental process, rather than just a traditional conventional didactic story system. This project, we apply Cognitive Poetic Approaches, developed by Peter Stockwell, to analyze three poems by Ted Hughes. The first one is "Peleus and Thetis", the second one is "Arachne", and the last is "Ravens". We can see how Cognitive Poetics offers a framework for understanding how readers mentally construct meaning through text worlds, schemas, conceptual metaphors, didactic positioning, and figure-ground organization. Those are shown in Ted Hughes' poems, functioning as cognitive parables, making the readers be in the process of transformation, empathy, and self-reflection.

First of all, in cognitive poetics, figure and ground organization is one of the important things to take into consideration. It refers to how certain elements of text are foregrounded while others stay into the background, making the reader's attention and interpretation into one direction. In Hughes mythological poetry, violence, transformation, and imagery function

as a figure. When social or divine order remains the ground. In Peleus and Thetis, Thetis shifting forms, becoming, fire, water, tree, those kind of elemental forces are foregrounded.

"She became flame, she became water, She became a lioness." (Ted Hughes, Peleus and Thetis)

The reader's attention is drawn to Thetis' metamorphosis rather than Peleus' intention to possess her. This change foregrounds female character and its stamina instead of having the traditional patriarchal mythic structures, not paying attention to Peleus, but rather having Thetis as a main metamorphosis, the main character. In Arachne, her weaving actions become the figure, while divine authority forms the ground. Peleus makes sensory imagery, for example, threads, tension, and motion so that the creation itself dominates the perceptive opinions of the reader. Athena's control remains present but mainly backgrounded, which allows the readers to cognitively align with Arachne's creative impulse. In the Ravens, Death and Predator are foregrounded through physical imagery of the dead lamb, while normality stays in the ground. This reverses, romanticizes the views of nature and forces the readers to perceive mortality as the central cognitive focus.

In Cognitive Poetics, prototype theory tells how readers understand text by comparing characters, events, and situations to daily, typical, or central examples which are put for centuries in their cognitive memory. According to Stockwell, readers read the literary text with prototypical expectations, which are shaped by cultural knowledge, genre, prior reading experience, or conventions. Meaning moves when these expectations are either fulfilled or more powerfully disturbed. Ted Hughes' mythological poetry especially works through prototype deviation, making it a very specific feature of his postmodern myth-making. Here are the typical mythic prototypes and their disruption in Ted Hughes' works. Hughes usually makes these prototypes into an active process of interpretation of psychology. Classical myths usually rely on stable prototypes. For instance, gods are powerful and authoritative, mortals are obedient and sometimes punished. Nature is symbolic, but in Ted Hughes' Peleus and Thetis, the prototype of the bride is disrupted. Traditionally, bride is expected to submit to marriage and accept its destiny. However, Thetis is unlike others. She is resisting and transformative from becoming bride. She is fire, water, element, animal. This non-prototypical behavior breaks the reader's expectation of female passivity in mythical stories. Instead, it puts the female autonomy and resistance. From a cognitive perspective, this causes schema conflict. Readers should connect the marriage-myth schema and understand the poem as a struggle over identity and bodily sovereignty rather than romantic union. Reading becomes a process of schema refreshment when postmodern myth is reconstructed with the new psychological depth. In Ravens, Hughes aggressively makes the reader expectations by destroying the pastoral prototype. The usual traditional farms and rural life should be gentle, innocent and harmonious. Readers approach, read the poem, expecting these things, especially when the newborn lambs were born, they think, they feel the softness. But Hughes changes it. He chooses graphic death. A lamb is born dead and it is disemboweled by ravens.

"A lamb of an hour or two, born dead". (Ted Hughes, Ravens)

This violent prototype violation makes emotional shock and cognitive dissonance. The readers should forget about the pastoral schema and construct a new understanding of nature as morally indifferent rather than nurturing and soft. The child's repeated question in the poem, which is, " - Did it cry?" It makes the more disruption. Children are prototypically associated

with innocence and emotional clarity. Here brutality is put without explanation. The reader is forced into an ethical reading position and rethink about assumption of life, death and meaning. From a cognitive poetic perspective, this is what makes Hughes' work postmodern mythology. Ancient stories are rewritten not as just fixed narratives but as open cognitive structures where the reader get the meaning through disruption, and the readers have the reflection through those schema refreshments.

References:

1. Hughes T. Tales from Ovid: Twenty-Four Passages from the Metamorphoses. – London: Faber & Faber, 1997. – 208 p.
2. Hughes T. Poetry in the Making: An Anthology. – London: Faber & Faber, 1967. – 120 p.
3. Lakoff G., Johnson M. Metaphors We Live By. – Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980. – 256 p.
4. Stockwell P. Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction. – London: Routledge, 2002. – 193 p.